

Theoretical investigations of the reaction kinetics and mechanism for the Cl initiated oxidation of $\text{CF}_3\text{C}(\text{O})\text{CH}_2\text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_3$

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ABSTRACT

A detailed quantum chemical study was carried out to unravel the reaction mechanism, kinetics, and thermochemistry governing the gas-phase oxidation of 1,1,1-trifluoro-hexane-2,4-dione ($\text{CF}_3\text{C}(\text{O})\text{CH}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$, TFH) by Cl radical, employing the M06-2X density functional. The most thermodynamically stable conformer of TFH was identified under ambient conditions. Three predominant hydrogen-abstraction channels were characterized, both involving the formation of pre-reactive complexes, thereby indicating an indirect abstraction mechanism. Temperature-dependent rate coefficients for these pathways were computed for the first time over the 250–450 K temperature range using Canonical Transition State Theory (CTST). Our result Based on the calculated kinetic parameters, the atmospheric lifetime of TFH was estimated to be approximately 24 hrs.

Keywords: Fluorinated diketone, DFT, Rate constant, Atmospheric life time.

INTRODUCTION

Environmental attention to the atmospheric behavior and transformation of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) emitted from human activities has intensified in recent years, largely as a consequence of rapid population expansion and industrial development. Following their release, VOCs are removed from the troposphere through multiple pathways, including physical processes such as wet and dry deposition, as well as chemical degradation driven by atmospheric oxidation. Photooxidative reactions initiated by hydroxyl ($\cdot\text{OH}$) radicals, chlorine ($\cdot\text{Cl}$) atoms, nitrate (NO_3) radicals, and ozone (O_3) represent the dominant chemical loss mechanisms and typically proceed via hydrogen abstraction or addition to unsaturated carbon bonds. Oxygenated volatile organic compounds (OVOCs), which arise both from primary emissions and secondary oxidation processes, are central to atmospheric photochemistry. Ketones constitute a significant subgroup of oxygenated volatile organic compounds (OVOCs) and originate from both anthropogenic and natural sources, including industrial processes, vehicular emissions [1-3], and the metabolic breakdown of biomass. In the atmosphere, ketones are primarily removed through photolytic processes that generate reactive radical species or via reactions with reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to the formation of aldehydes, organic acids, and other low-volatility products.

Fluorinated diketones (FDKs) are widely utilized in the synthesis of pharmaceuticals, advanced dyes, surface coatings, and metallurgical applications, where they frequently serve as chelating agents [4]. Certain industrial uses, particularly those involving metal-organic chemical vapor deposition techniques, represent potential emission sources of these compounds into the atmosphere [5]. The presence of both carbon-fluorine bonds and carbonyl functional groups in FDKs suggests that they may exhibit non-negligible global

warming potential. Among these compounds, kinetic investigations of the reaction between 1,1,1-trifluoro-pentane-2,4-dione (TFH) and Cl radical have been experimentally reported. Lego *et al.* [6] reported a value of $1.19 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at $(298 \pm 2) \text{ K}$ by FTIR spectroscopy technique for the keto-form of TFH. However, despite these experimental efforts, a detailed theoretical description of the oxidation mechanism of TFH initiated by Cl radicals is still lacking. In this context, the present study aims to provide a comprehensive mechanistic and kinetic characterization of the Cl-initiated oxidation of TFH using advanced quantum chemical methodologies. Based on the above discussion, the objective of this study is to explore the oxidation mechanism and kinetic parameters of TFH using a robust quantum chemical methodology. The oxidation process is initiated by Cl radical through hydrogen atom abstraction, which can occur at the $-\text{CH}_2$, $-\text{C}(\text{O})\text{CH}_2$ or $-\text{CH}_3$ positions of TFH, giving rise to two alternative reaction channels as shown in Scheme 1

Scheme 1: Oxidation of TFH initiated by Cl radical

In the present study, density functional theory (DFT) calculations were carried out to evaluate the energetic profiles, optimized geometries, and harmonic vibrational frequencies of the reactants, products, and transition states associated with the hydrogen-abstraction reactions of keto form of TFH.

COMPUTATIONAL METHODS

All electronic structure computations were carried out using the Gaussian 09 software package [7]. Density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed employing the M06-2X hybrid functional [8] in conjunction with the 6-31+G(d,p) basis set. The M06-2X functional is well recognized for its reliable performance in predicting thermochemical properties and reaction kinetics and has demonstrated good agreement with experimental and theoretical results in numerous prior studies [9-14]. Harmonic vibrational frequency analyses were conducted at the same level of theory to characterize the nature of the optimized stationary points and to obtain zero-point energy corrections. These calculations confirmed that stable species correspond to true minima with no imaginary frequencies, whereas each transition state exhibits a single imaginary frequency associated with the reaction coordinate. Intrinsic reaction coordinate (IRC) calculations [15] were further performed to ensure that each transition state properly connects the relevant reactant and product minima. Using the optimized geometries obtained at the M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level, more accurate single-point energy calculations were subsequently carried out and the resulting energies were used to evaluate the relative energy differences (ΔE) among all stationary points.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level, the calculated thermodynamic data for the species has been recorded in Table 1. The reaction enthalpies ($\Delta_r H^\circ$) and free energies ($\Delta_r G^\circ$) at 298 K for loss processes (1–2) are documented in Table 1. These thermodynamic functions were determined with thermal corrections to the energy at 298 K. The calculated $\Delta_r H^\circ$ and $\Delta_r G^\circ$ values at 298 K indicate that the decomposition pathways taken into consideration in this investigation are feasible and spontaneous. It is evident from Table 1 that the reaction channel 2

is more thermodynamically viable. Because $\Delta_r H^\circ_{298} < 0$, the results also show that reaction channels (1–2) are exothermic in nature.

In order to identify, the most stable conformer of TFH scan calculation has been performed by rotating dihedral angle (C6-C5-C1-C12) and the most stable conformer of TFH has taken in consideration for further study. The result obtained during scan calculation has been depicted in Figure 1. For the hydrogen abstraction reactions, we have considered three reaction routes (1–3), mainly hydrogen abstraction from the $-\text{CH}_2$ group, $-\text{C}(\text{O})\text{CH}_2$ group and $-\text{CH}_3$ group. Pre-reactive complexes (RC1, RC2 and RC3) have been found in the entrance channel for reactions (1–3) in the current investigation. The exit channel also contains product complexes, referred to as PC1, PC2 and PC3, before the final product is distributed. The C–H bond of the departing hydrogen and the newly generated bond between the H and Cl atom are crucial structural characteristics that must be monitored throughout the development of transition states. Figure 2 shows the electronic structure of the optimized geometry of the reactant, products, reaction complexes, product complexes, and transition states that were produced at the M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level. Visualization of the electronic structure of optimized geometry of TS1 corresponding to reaction channel (1) it has been observed that the breaking C–H (C5– H10) bond length is 17.07% greater than the observed C–H bond length in the isolated TFH molecule, while the forming H...Cl bond length is 21.40% longer than the H–Cl bond length in isolated HCl molecule, This implies that the barrier of the reaction 1 is closer to the reactant. It is emphasized that the reactions with Cl atom proceed via early transition state which is in consonance with Hammond's postulate [16]. Similarly, for transition state TS2 for reaction channel 2, the length of the breaking C–H bond (C12 –H14) is found to be elongated by 16.01% than the observed C –H bond length in isolated TFH molecule whereas the forming H...Cl bond length is longer by 23.13% than the H–Cl bond length in isolated HCl

molecule. This implies that the barrier of the reaction 2 is closer to the reactant, and that the reactions with Cl atoms proceed via early transition state. Similar visualization for the transition state TS3 corresponding to reaction channel (3) reveals that the breaking C-H bond (C15–H16) is elongated by 36.99% while the forming H...Cl bond length is longer by 10.46%.

Table 2 presents the results of the harmonic vibrational frequency calculation at the M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level. Each transition state has one imaginary frequency due to its first order saddle point character, while the analysis of the harmonic vibrational frequency of minima including reactants, reactant complexes (RCs), product complexes (PCs), and products (P1 and P2) revealed no imaginary frequency (NIMAG = 0). The C119–H10 and C5–H10 stretching modes are represented by the imaginary frequency of TS1 for reaction channel (1), which is 999 cm^{-1} . This also shows a considerable curvature in the potential energy surface (PES) surrounding the transition state. The imaginary frequency for the hydrogen abstraction from the $-\text{C}(\text{O})\text{CH}_2$ group involving TS2 is determined to be 642 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the stretching modes for hydrogen transfer reaction C119–H14 and C12–H14. The imaginary frequency for TS3 is found to be 621 cm^{-1} which corresponds to stretching modes for C119–H16 and C15–H16.

The representation of the normal-mode corresponding to the calculated imaginary frequencies shows a clear transition state geometry connecting reactants and products during transition. To further ascertain whether a transition state exists on the potential energy surface, the intrinsic reaction coordinate (IRC) calculation [15] is performed at the same theoretical level using the Gonzalez-Schlegel steepest descent path in the mass-weighted Cartesian coordinates with a step size of $0.01(\text{amu}^{1/2}\text{- bohr})$. Additional proof that the transition state truly connects the intended reactant and product along the corresponding potential energy surface is given by the results of IRC calculations, which are shown in Figure 3. Table 3

summarizes the energy of each optimized geometry obtained during present study, at M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p), level of method. In order to compute zero-point energy (ZPE) for stationary points, we have performed frequency calculation at the M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory. Zero-point energy (ZPE) thus obtained were corrected with a scale factor of 0.967 [17] and the total energies of each species were calculated on potential energy surface. Figure 4 shows a schematic potential energy profile of TFH reactivity with the Cl radical using zero-point energy (ZPE) corrections. The ground state energy of TFH + Cl, which includes ZPE, is plotted against these energies, with zero being used randomly. For TS1, TS2 and TS3 the energy barrier determined at the M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level is 0.55, -4.90 and 0.51 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively. From these results, it can be emphasize that the hydrogen abstraction from the -C(O)CH₂ group is more facile than the hydrogen abstraction from -CH₃ group. It is in accordance with the experimental finding of Lugo et al. [6].

Kinetics calculation

The conventional transition state theory (CTST) [18] and Eckart's tunneling correction [19] were used to calculate the rate coefficient values for various reaction channels spanning the 250–450 K temperature range using the following formula.

$$k = \sigma \Gamma(T) \frac{k_B T}{h} \frac{Q_{TS}^\ddagger}{Q_R} \exp \frac{-\Delta E}{RT} \quad (4)$$

The σ represents symmetry factor whereas tunneling correction factor at temperature T is represented by the symbol $\Gamma(T)$. The total partition functions (per unit volume) for the reactants and transition states are denoted by Q_R and Q_{TS}^\ddagger , respectively. R stands for the universal gas constant, k_B for the Boltzmann constant, h for Planck's constant, and ΔE for the barrier height incorporating zero point energy correction. The value of symmetry factor for reaction channels (1–3) has been taken as 2, 2 and 3, respectively. The obtained rate coefficients in the

temperature range of 250 – 450 K for reaction pathways (1–3) are recorded in Table 4. At 298 K, our calculated rate constants for TS1, TS2 and TS3 were found to be 2.23×10^{-12} , 3.09×10^{-10} and $3.63 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively at M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory. The computed overall k_{Cl} value at 298 K is found to be $3.15 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for TFH with Cl reaction. Our calculated rate constant for the reaction of TFH with Cl radical is in good agreement with the reported value of $1.19 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at $(298 \pm 2) \text{ K}$ by Lugo et al. [6] The percentage branching ratios for each of the reaction channels determined at 298 K are found to be 0.70, 98.14 and 1.15 %, respectively. From these results, it can be emphasize that the hydrogen abstraction from the $-\text{C}(\text{O})\text{CH}_2$ group is kinetically more advantageous than the other reaction pathways.

Atmospheric lifetime

In general, tropospheric lifetime (τ_{eff}) of TFH can be estimated by assuming that its removal from troposphere occurs only through the reactions with Cl atoms. Then (τ_{eff}) can be expressed as [20],

$$\tau_{\text{eff}} = \tau_{\text{Cl}}$$

where, $\tau_{\text{Cl}} = (k_{\text{Cl}} \times [\text{Cl}])^{-1}$. Using the 298 K value of $k_{\text{Cl}} = 3.15 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and the global average atmospheric Cl concentrations of $3.3 \times 10^4 \text{ molecule cm}^{-3}$ [21], the estimated atmospheric lifetime of TFH is found to be 26 hours.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the present study provides a comprehensive potential energy surface and rate constant data for the atmospheric and environmental consequence of TFH molecule initiated by Cl radical by employing M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory. We have done various inquires involving the optimization of structural parameters, energy profiles, thermochemistry, and kinetics of the TFH with Cl radical. For that, we have identified three

reaction channels which follow an indirect path through the formation of pre- and post- reaction complexes on the potential energy surface. All rate constants, computed by canonical transition state theory are in reasonable agreement with the limited experimental data. The thermal rate constant for the H atom abstraction of TFH by Cl radical is found to be $3.15 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 298 K. Our results suggest that hydrogen abstraction from the $-\text{C}(\text{O})\text{CH}_2$ group is likely the dominant route for Cl-initiated oxidation of TFH under reaction conditions. The atmospheric lifetime for TFH molecule is estimated to be 26 hours.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Table1 Thermochemical data for reaction channels (1–3) calculated at M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory. All values are in kcal mol⁻¹.

Reaction channels	$\Delta_r H^\circ$	$\Delta_r G^\circ$
Reaction 1	-10.10	-11.30
Reaction 2	-10.69	-12.79
Reaction 3	2.68	0.12

Table 2 Harmonic vibrational frequencies of reactants, transition states and products at M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory.

Species	Vibrational Frequencies (cm ⁻¹)
TFH	16, 44, 59, 73, 135, 184, 209, 228, 248, 327, 392, 425, 493, 497, 559, 608, 638, 714, 778, 795, 858, 924, 1014, 1041, 1081, 1105, 1145, 1224, 13234, 1270, 1288, 1322, 1391, 1408, 1425, 1443, 1461, 1499, 1506, 1869, 1912, 3056, 3078, 3081, 3100, 3139, 3163, 3166
TS1	999i, 26, 30, 42, 60, 70, 108, 126, 185, 223, 228, 263, 322, 361, 433, 473, 496, 508, 561, 634, 638, 731, 770, 787, 847, 870, 943, 1016, 1055, 1102, 1108, 1164, 1180, 1234, 1280, 1287, 1322, 1398, 1413, 1429, 1459, 1504, 1508, 1833, 1873, 3074, 3082, 3112, 3164, 3168, 3171
TS2	642i, 19, 43, 50, 61, 72, 125, 146, 181, 206, 234, 254, 350, 378, 431, 456, 504, 536, 563, 606, 649, 760, 784, 790, 843, 922, 965, 1034, 1063, 1073, 1112, 1158, 1207, 1214, 1228, 1288, 1310, 1384, 1398, 1417, 1463, 1482, 1838, 1907, 3061, 3083, 3142, 3162, 3180, 3183
TS3	621i, 21, 31, 48, 52, 67, 80, 144, 195, 204, 229, 325, 385, 391, 426, 495, 498, 558, 609, 633, 686, 709, 755, 784, 844, 845, 865, 935, 1036, 1075, 1095, 1115, 1196, 1231, 1236, 1272, 1295, 1320, 1361, 1402, 1443, 1452, 1485, 1870, 1908, 3063, 3077, 3120, 3142, 3158, 3264
RC1	31, 44, 48, 66, 82, 87, 101, 151, 191, 221, 232, 259, 327, 401, 427, 495, 500, 558, 608, 637, 720, 784, 797, 859, 924, 1011, 1041, 1084, 1103, 1151, 1223, 1272, 1288, 1324, 1370, 1408, 1422, 1449, 1479, 1502, 1505, 1867, 1910, 3032, 3066, 3084, 3085, 3140, 3164, 3173,
RC2	18, 27, 45, 67, 79, 91, 138, 163, 187, 231, 247, 284, 330, 397, 428, 496, 505, 559, 612, 633, 710, 770, 792, 855, 920, 1005, 1031, 1050, 1101, 1108, 1160, 1176, 1230, 1240, 1283, 1323, 1379, 1409, 1418, 1442, 1482, 1485, 1590, 1854, 1906, 3069, 3069, 3138, 3146, 3147, 3176
RC3	11, 23, 27, 46, 58, 77, 88, 139, 182, 211, 231, 255, 329, 395, 426, 496, 506, 558, 611, 635, 716, 775, 796, 857, 928, 1015, 1042, 1084, 1106, 1139, 1223, 1235, 1270, 1289, 1321, 1381, 1404, 1421, 1440, 1459, 1496, 1504, 1870, 1911, 3025, 3074, 3080, 3143, 3164, 3165

PC1	29, 41, 43, 49, 97, 101, 123, 128, 198, 225, 252, 288, 331, 389, 438, 445, 500, 511, 557, 584, 646, 657, 742, 770, 796, 835, 897, 1016, 1081, 1097, 1116, 1207, 1229, 1278, 1289, 1336, 1402, 1429, 1441, 1459, 1503, 1506, 1728, 1750, 2774, 3075, 3079, 3110, 3163, 3221
PC2	18, 26, 46, 62, 69, 89, 98, 110, 171, 209, 232, 254, 330, 400, 429, 473, 495, 525, 550, 562, 611, 646, 667, 752, 843, 856, 937, 996, 1046, 1085, 1108, 1176, 1229, 1252, 1281, 1323, 1397, 1407, 1441, 1470, 1480, 1506, 1669, 1911, 2687, 3052, 3075, 3107, 3149, 3179, 3239
PC3	20, 28, 46, 49, 56, 81, 92, 141, 172, 197, 229, 263, 329, 376, 394, 426, 473, 494, 498, 558, 610, 626, 696, 726, 780, 821, 858, 940, 1039, 1077, 1099, 1116, 1222, 1235, 1271, 1291, 1318, 1350, 1402, 1443, 1487, 1872, 1908, 2696, 3044, 3076, 3112, 3146, 3186, 3296
HCl	3033
CF ₃ C(O)CH COCH ₂ CH ₃ (P1)	31, 44, 97, 120, 128, 193, 232, 256, 279, 328, 383, 445, 496, 510, 555, 642, 650, 743, 768, 793, 831, 894, 1019, 1083, 1094, 1114, 1199, 1226, 1283, 1286, 1331, 1395, 1429, 1449, 1458, 1501, 1508, 1730, 1747, 3077, 3079, 3113, 3161, 3165, 3232
CF ₃ C(O)CH ₂ COCHCH ₃ (P2)	30, 41, 64, 80, 95, 171, 202, 233, 269, 332, 394, 429, 496, 545, 560, 614, 643, 675, 754, 813, 857, 935, 995, 1043, 1055, 1125, 1177, 1228, 1246, 1279, 1320, 1397, 1404, 1439, 1451, 1480, 1516, 1659, 1905, 3050, 3074, 3105, 3144, 3180, 3217
CF ₃ C(O)CH ₂ COCH ₂ CH ₂ (P3)	23, 45, 54, 72, 138, 166, 191, 228, 249, 327, 389, 425, 485, 495, 533, 566, 609, 658, 714, 777, 811, 854, 933, 1039, 1076, 1103, 1115, 1220, 1232, 1267, 1285, 1316, 1342, 1404, 1443, 1446, 1486, 1870, 1911, 3040, 3079, 3099, 3139, 3197, 3306

Table 3 Relative energies (in kcal mol⁻¹) with zero-point energy correction for the reactants, reaction complexes, transition states, product complexes and products at M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory.

Species	M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p)
TFH + Cl	0
RC1	-2.57
RC2	-1.68
RC3	-4.10
TS1	0.55
TS2	-4.90
TS3	0.51
PC1	-15.15
PC2	-16.64
PC3	-0.69
P1 + HCl	-10.33
P2 + HCl	-11.12
P3 + HCl	2.07

Table 4: Rate constants of different reaction channels and overall rate constant (in $\text{cm}^3 \text{molecule}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) within the temperature range of 250–450 K at M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory.

Rate constant	250 K	298.15 K	300 K	350 K	400 K	450 K
k₁	2.30×10^{-12}	2.23×10^{-12}	2.22×10^{-12}	2.31×10^{-12}	2.48×10^{-12}	2.71×10^{-12}
k₂	1.97×10^{-9}	3.09×10^{-10}	2.91×10^{-10}	8.04×10^{-11}	3.20×10^{-11}	1.60×10^{-11}
k₃	2.57×10^{-12}	3.63×10^{-12}	3.67×10^{-12}	4.85×10^{-12}	6.08×10^{-12}	7.36×10^{-12}
k_{overall}	1.98×10^{-9}	3.15×10^{-10}	2.98×10^{-10}	8.77×10^{-11}	4.06×10^{-11}	2.61×10^{-11}

Figure 1: The electronic energy of different conformers of TFH vs. dihedral angle C5-C1-C12-C15 at M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory.

CF₃C(O)CH₂C(O)CH₂CH₃

TS1

TS2

TS3

RC1

RC2

RC3

PC1

..... Continue

PC2

PC3

CF₃C(O)CH₂C(O)CH₂CH₂ (P3)

Figure 2: Optimized geometry of reactants, reaction complexes, transition states, product complexes and products obtained at M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory. Bond lengths are in angstroms.

Figure 3: IRC plots performed for transition states TS1, TS2 and TS3 obtained at M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory.

Figure 4: Potential energy diagram for the reaction of Cl radical with TFH at M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory.